

Designing for Safety: A Review of Human-Centered Approaches in Evacuation App Development

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Abstract:

This review focuses on the development of evacuation apps used in emergencies with the principal role of User-Centered Design (UCD). With intensifying dependence on technological growth, precisely emergency evacuation scenarios, these apps are helpful for their usage and design. This study sheds light on the importance of user experience by designing human-centric elements and integrating them into user experience. It is ensured explicitly that their accessibility and effectiveness during high-stress situations do not impact the app's functionality. Existing apps lack interface usability regarding human-centric approaches, present inconsistent information, and lack disability and demographic integration, causing a bad user experience. Incorporation of UCD principles of usability, user needs, and iterative design, the design of more inclusive and responsive apps meets these critical challenges identified in the review. The recommendations, thus provided, help improve functionality as well as usability. The objective of this paper is to support the development of user-friendly apps facilitating users during emergencies following an in-depth literature review of such apps being used in such scenarios.

Keywords: *User-Centered-Design, Evacuation Application, Mobile Application Design, User experience.*

Introduction

The widespread use of technology has permeated daily life to the extent that even emergencies are now managed using apps readily available on public markets like Google Play Store. This has led to the emergence of apps that can also be used in emergency evacuation situations (Alexander, 2015). Urbanization and interconnectedness of modern cities have led to timely information sharing among people (Li, et al., 2018). Safety, a critical issue, has also invited

coders' attention regarding developing such apps to ensure safe evacuation. This has come in handy when designing evacuation apps and in terms of design, usability, and human-centric approaches to the cornerstones (Romano, et al., 2016; Omaier, et al., 2019).

Top of it is the User Experience advancement for user-friendly or centered design (Figueiredo, 2019). This enhances safety assurance during critical emergency evacuation scenarios (Omaier, et al., 2019). Designing apps with user-centric

approaches has benefits in effectiveness, accessibility, and user-centricity (Biswas, Robinson, & Langdon, 2012). Regarding decision-making, emergency evacuation apps ensure public safety and safe exit. In such critical situations, the significance of User-Centered Design (UCD) multiplies (Sarshar, Radianti, & Gonzalez, 2015). Despite the complexity of the technology used during these emergencies, effectiveness and user-centered approaches in designing apps have become essential to meet the users' requirements in such situations, as well as their cognitive capacities and critical decision-making ability (Sarshar, Radianti, & Gonzalez, 2015; Sarshar, Nunavath, & Radianti, 2015). This priority comes at the top of the list in its designing cycle, ensuring that functioning, interface design, and information retrieval or delivery facilitate when it comes to stressful environmental usage of these apps (Tan, et al., 2020). If they have auto-adjustment functions to ever-changing user requirements following iterative design with feedback and usability testing, then such apps deliver the best results (Kamilaris, et al., 2023). This short review aims to explore the specialized task of considering UX design, suggesting new and optimized designs to facilitate user experience with a human-centric approach.

Although Google PlayStore is full of emergency evacuation apps, a gap exists regarding features such as UX for widespread adoption and effectiveness of usability. The first such review was provided by Al Bochi, et al. (2023) who indicate shortcomings in the current landscape of these apps. They state that such apps have interfaces with unintuitive features, provide information inconsistently, and lack consideration for disability and demographic diversity. The exclusion of these features leads to less optimization of user experience, making users switch to multiple apps due to the impediments the absence of such features places on their usage. Additionally, two other issues accessibility and technological literacy further

impact these impediments and raise additional roadblocks, affecting the distribution of information and services equally for all users (Freeman, Park, & Middleton, 2020). Due to the significance of these apps for public safety, it becomes imperative to remove these roadblocks through targeted research and design interventions to optimize the use of such apps during emergency evacuation efforts (Ferris, et al., 2016).

As is the case, removing these roadblocks requires the adoption of human-centric designs and principles (Tan, et al., 2020). It means placing the user at the front of the design process and focusing on its usability, accessibility, and empathetic thinking of human emotions (Boy, 2017). When used in emergency contextual situations, it becomes relevant that it is appropriate to the stress level individuals experience during emergencies and how they find its usability facilitating in evacuation environments (Haghani, Sarvi, & Shahhoseini, 2020). Such requires considerations of psychological issues, cognition, and user behavior to be included in the study and design process to develop an interface that aligns not only with the users' requirements but also their mental capability, facilitating intuitive interactions. Catarci et al. (2020) study sheds light on the shift towards crowd-based and user-centric design to optimize the usability of such apps used for emergency evacuation. Their primary focus is on the importance of users' feedback along with iterative testing and adaptive design techniques, as shown in Figure 1.

Based on this new strategic thinking, this paper aims to contribute to the ongoing growth of such apps with a comprehensive and in-depth investigation of human-centric principles and techniques used in the design process. The primary purpose of this approach is to meet the challenges emergency evacuation poses in such situations to ensure the safety and user-friendliness of the users during a crisis.

Figure 1. Depicts the Steps Involved in User-Centered Design (UCD) Principles. The Diagram Outlines the Sequential Process from Gathering User Feedback to Testing the Final Application

Literature Review

With recurrent catastrophic happenings across the globe coinciding with the intensification of urbanization, emergency evacuation apps, specifically for androids, have also multiplied, and their significance has skyrocketed. This literature review investigates the complexity of scenarios in which their functionality occurs, their effectiveness in evacuation efforts, their qualitative usage and their UCD principles, which facilitate their usage in removing roadblocks. It also focuses on the significance of this technological improvement, which caters to a wide array of users, removing roadblocks in usage and facilitating swift evacuation during crises. This review specifically concentrates on how the research reviewed below demonstrates different features and deeper insight into the making and designing of these apps.

Evolution of Emergency Evacuation Apps in Disaster Management

Whereas smartphones have become part and parcel of life, so are apps working to cater to the different requirements of the users. Their functionality has also crept into the emergency evacuation plans in major urban centers where mammoth buildings house thousands of individuals and fast evacuation during emergencies becomes problematic (Paul, Bee, & Budimir, 2021). During these situations, these emergency evacuation apps offer practical, swift and facilitative solutions to the evacuation problem (Radianti, et al., 2013). Their prevalent and wide usage could be attributed to the easy-to-use interface of smartphones. Therefore, their widespread usage could be attributed to effective

evacuation, as Liu et al. (2016) state in their research with Al-Akkad et al. (2011) adding that functions of human sensors provide real-time information to these apps. However, he focuses on a mobile assisting system that works better. However, Omaier et al. (2019) contend that apps have different features and, consequently, different functions, which are essential to understanding the capabilities of each app and their effectiveness in evacuation plans.

Essential Features and Capabilities of Emergency Evacuation Apps

Evacuation planning apps offer a wide range of features and capabilities. Their primary purpose is to meet the significant requirements of the end users to make their evacuation safe and sound. According to Sikder et al. (2017) alarms and notifications or real-time notifications are two primary critical elements in an evacuation app. He also presents ways toward shelter houses and evacuation protocols in his research, which, according to him, are impactful. Similarly, Bernardini et al. (2017) state that interactive maps make evacuation facilitative and easy. However, their research focuses on the literature on technological gadgets and internet connectivity as two roadblocks. Ryan et al. (2020) state that if the community is involved in such plans, it disseminates such information quickly and widely to most users. Therefore, utilizing UCD methodology to make a prototype of intelligent systems is of paramount importance.

On the other hand, Ortakci et al. (2017) state that accessibility is a critical feature. Understanding its features is crucial to

understanding the app. Therefore, his argument of accessibility has laid the foundation for examining how to improve users' experience when designing a human-centric interface or at least using this approach.

Integrating User-Centered Design Principles in Emergency Evacuation App Development

Whereas UCD is concerned, it is a design concept. Its major priority is the requirements of the end users of these apps. It means how a user puts things, functions, or elements on the top and then behaves likewise to have an interface designed during the development process (Carroll, & Rosson, 2014). It means constant or iterative testing and refining it constantly while understanding the users' requirements and adapting to them in usability. Also, users' feedback must be incorporated during this priority in designing. Regarding its significance, Li, et al., (2018) states that products must be facilitative for users who can understand them, learn them quickly, and use them effectively. Therefore, according to him, this usability must be focused during the design process to make such an evacuation an effective app for evacuation. However, Zhang et al. (2023) argues that empathy also plays an important role, as users are often in stressful states with high emotions during catastrophic events. Therefore, empathy during design must be kept in mind. However, Mendez-Gurrola et al. (2023) state that constant testing following the design process makes usability easy and ensures that app adaptation meets the requirements and expectations of users as its responsiveness becomes easy and fast. Regarding architectural issues, Stigall et al. (2019) Stress upon the requirement of compactness and accessible structure, which, they declare, is of critical significance for spreading information fast during such stressful situations.

Gai et al. (2018) argue that adaptation in design synchronizes with emergencies due to their swift and effective responses in such evacuations. Another thing that must be kept in mind is the collaboration of the designers and the emergency managers, who understand such

situations better than designers. Marella et al. (2011) state that this collaboration or its synergy is of critical importance during emergencies and that this requires effective, fast and clear communication. Integrating all of these principals, suggestions and elements into evacuation apps or apps equipped with these critical components proves facilitatively effective not only in functions but also in user usage, accessibility and empowerment of end users.

Evolving Difficulties and Shortcomings in Evacuation Apps: Insights and Recommendations

Research has indicated challenges and roadblocks in evacuation apps, showing areas inviting further improvements and changes. Kuo et al. (2022) highlight that a more inclusive method is required for future apps. They believe such apps require diversity due to the requirements of each being different and that they are required to remove functional limitations. Ensuring that apps are universally accessible and provide tailored support for different demographics remains a pressing dispute, as he mentioned that smoke reduces visibility in emergencies, so we should cater for this with a diverse approach. Cognitive overload for users due to inundated information during catastrophic events requires focused attention. This presents a challenging aspect of showing critical information concisely and targeted.

An experiment conducted in a virtual environment by Xia et al. (2021) shows that such an interface design responsible for cognitive reduction load is possible. It allows its users to make critical decisions quickly in a stressful environment. Another research study by Cotfas et al. (2023) believes that evacuation from cruise liners should focus on real-time adaptation to the existing scenario. This research focuses on agent-based models for making critical decisions and improving adaptation to real-time scenarios during such situations. This means including various circumstances in the apps and using complete and extensive information regarding real-time adaptation. Ronchi et al. (2019) have conducted a workshop about new approaches for evacuation modelling, stating that technological and literary differences are of

critical significance in fire safety engineering apps. They highlight the importance of incorporating experiences from other disciplines consisting of psychology, mathematics, sociology and dynamic simulation for further improvements in modelling such evacuation apps.

Methods

Following the lines set by UCD principles, the features demonstrated in (Table 1) have curated all the necessary elements of effectiveness, usability and user experience when using evacuation apps. These features include critical aspects of emergency responses, state of preparation, timely alerts, assistance to users toward safe places, first aid instructions, and communication ease. The focus, as aligned with these principles, is to tailor these features to meet users' needs, considering their diversity and stressful confrontations with such scenarios.

Most of the apps analyzed have been collected, as shown in Table 1 (Appendix), from the Google Play Store¹ and the Apple App Store². A selection process incorporating criteria include user ratings, download count numbers and reviews on Google Play Store and Apple Store were considered. Real-time notifications, routes, contacts, and survival tips were also considered. Some other elements considered during the choice of apps were functions synchronized with the type of disaster and its management, GPS tracking system, offline accessibility of maps and communication tools. Besides ranking the apps, other features, which include prioritization of scenarios and comprehensiveness, were also given priority. Keywords used when selecting apps include emergency evacuation, disaster preparedness, evacuation app, and evacuation routes for relevance, indexed online search engines, curated lists, suggestions from disaster management organizations, and academic scholarship. This whole process ensured a wide selection, covering various aspects of disaster management and evacuation protocols.

¹ For more information about the Google Play Store, see: <https://play.google.com/store>.

Observation and Discussion

This section will present our observations and insights into the best practices employed in different domains and pinpoint crucial areas needing improvement.

Additionally, it will offer guidance for designing and developing these apps to maximize their effectiveness, user-friendliness, and inclusivity. The primary goal is to enhance the functionality of these apps to ensure that they meet the end user's needs while following the fundamental principle of user-centered design approaches. Figure 2 depicts the overall utilization of the features in our collected apps.

Map Based Visualization

Eighty-two percent (14 out of 17) of the collected apps apply Map-Based Visualization, a crucial element of UCD for such evacuation scenarios. Therefore, it is evident that developers and designers both value it. Despite this, it is important to highlight that 20% of these apps do not show this feature included. Therefore, they may use users' judgement about the space setting in an emergency. This reviewed literature shows that map display is critical in such apps. For example, Cybulski, (2021) agree and suggest that the inclusion of this element is to optimize navigation during emergency evacuations. However, Du, et al. (2021) warn that maps could cause cognitive overload and strain mental faculties, specifically when users are in panic mode. Other scholars, like Cao et al. (2016) state that this map inclusion is critical as it provides a clear understanding of spatial information. It helps the decision-making process and saves users from outages. Nefros et al. (2018) also note that maps provide visual representations of the areas to the end users, helping them to plan safe evacuation and make strategies. Therefore, it is essential to create a balance between comprehensive information about evacuation space and the requirement of the app's user-friendly interface. Other features like interactive elements, easy labels and intuitive design help reduce the overloading of cognition, improving the users' experience when they are in

² For more information about the Apple App Store, see: <https://www.apple.com/ios/app-store/>.

an emergency. The result is that such apps should give priority to a user-centric approach during the designing process to guarantee that

users use spatial recognition successfully and navigate the way out of the crises even when they are in panic mode.

Figure 2. Illustrates the Number of Apps Incorporating Various Features. The y-Axis Indicates the Number of Apps We Collected, while the x-Axis Lists the Different Features We Research on It

Push Notification

Push notification features are extensively used. Around 82% (14 out of 17) of the total apps analyzed reveal this feature. UCD principles state that these push notifications are acknowledged as necessary for users' facilitation as studies of Dirgahayu et al. (2021) support this argument, which proves that push notifications provide handy alerts in real-time situations. These notifications also guarantee the users by giving complete updates about evacuation orders and alerts about routes on time. This helps the users to make decisions and ensure safety (Wu, et al., 2020). Push notifications are facilitating as they provide correct information about location and according to the users' requirements, for they are customized to these preferences and experiences and sync with the UCD principles. They also help users to be

confident, specifically when in critical situations, as Wu et al. (2020) argue about their feasibility in the design. Furthermore, Wohllebe, Adler, & Podrzensik, (2021) highlight their benefits if they are thoughtfully created for user engagement to indicate that this feature is in accordance with UCD principles and helps to improve user involvement in the app. Therefore, the advice is to include this notification in the apps at the top of the priority list to acknowledge that research shows a viable path for the design process. Therefore, developers should also keep in mind that these push notifications should sync with the users' requirements, situations, and priorities and that they adhere to the fundamental principles of UCD design. This also means delivering timely updates to make them relevant and prominent in clarity and understandable during stressful situations.

Shelter Guide Feature

Data analysis also demonstrates that apps have different Shelter Guide features integrated into them. Around 65% (11 out of 17) of apps show these features. This means that users will find easy access to the details of these areas, locations, and facilities available during crises. However, 35% (6 out of the 17) apps do not have this feature. It has also been found that more downloads are shown with apps having this feature. It shows that the Shelter Guide feature is an essential element of UCD design for evacuation apps. The reason is its two-fold benefit: it provides a good user experience and ensures users' safety. Some studies also support this argument. For example, Lin et al. (2020) highlight its criticality in evacuation apps, including other disciplinary knowledge, include psychology and sociology. This interdisciplinarity approach in the design process makes the Shelter Guide feature a complete solution that not only takes into account the specific needs of each user but also ensures safety. Tanaka et al. (2021) research state that the Shelter Guide not only improves accessibility but also provides awareness, giving users complete information about the neighborhood shelters to help them opt for the better and prevent overcrowding. These features contribute to a more efficient disaster response. Other research by Katsuya et al. (2021) indicates that real-time updates are also critical for such a feature because these updates provide users access to live information regarding shelters and help them decide quickly when making fast shifting during emergency scenarios. Nevertheless, another article by Suzianti et al. (2020) in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) emphasizes the importance of considering emotional aspects during the design process. Apps integrated with this function have good benefits for the users' mental health during emergencies. They follow the UCD principles and provide accurate shelter information, making users confident about their safety. This leads to good mental health. Hence, it is crucial to make users feel safe and confident and in mind to use the apps during such stressful scenarios.

Voice/Sound guidance Feature

Regarding sound features or voice guidance, it has been observed during this analysis that just 35% (6 out of 17) apps have these features. This revelation shows that there has been a lack of interest or ignore the importance of this feature, which shows disregard for disability, specifically people having visual impairment. This also goes against inclusivity and accessibility for all types of users. Let's shed light on this feature what researcher said about this and why they emphasize to align this feature according to UCD. Some researchers like Zhang et al. (2016) have stated that these features assist people to have critical information for their safety at the time of need. UCD guidelines and guarantees about all necessary information also include this feature, ensuring that the users are provided with necessary, direct and to-the-point information in their hour of need. Also, the impacts of such features have been explored in detail by Dong et al. (2018) in their research shows that the overall effectiveness of the app is based on sound features, taking users' understanding and reaction timing into consideration. This becomes clear that for future design, this feature must be given priority in UCD principles. This feature increases the users' overall experience and boosts the apps, making them precisely comply with the UCD principles for users with visual impairment issues. Ensuring that sound notifications are clear, distinct and audible ensures accessibility and inclusivity to be included in recommendations for the design process. In this connection, such software used in evacuation scenarios can enhance users' experience of safety and improve the effectiveness of the apps and their very objectives.

Pre-Emergency Notification Feature

Another vital feature is Pre-Emergency Notification or notification that alerts about an emergency just prior to it. The analysis demonstrates that 59% of apps (10 out of 17) have this feature. The criticality of notifying users to alert them about impending disasters or emergencies is of paramount importance. This means that the designers have a good knowledge

of the pre-alert features or information relayed just prior to such situations to alert the users. Therefore, this feature is essential to alert users during hazardous occasions and prepare them for an emergency. This is also named a proactive strategy that follows the UCD principles and makes the users psychologically aware to ensure safety and become aware of the situation. This advanced notification of alert decreases anxiety and panic. It allows management to organize empty evacuation routes, check essential supply items to cope with emergencies, and make users make fast decisions. Research by Chen et al. (2020) highlights how pre-emergency communication and alerts are early warning systems that boost users' response and preparation and give them timely notice to overcome uncertainty and improve their decision-making power in emergencies. Another study by Traya et al. (2022) has focused on how its inclusion enhances the apps facilitative design and increases the understanding of the users about this feature and its importance. However, issues that need to be resolved occasionally and must require redressal. For example, Xia et al. (2021) state that if users receive too many alerts or entirely irrelevant alerts about even minor issues, they would not be taking this feature seriously. This could lead to users being overloaded during an emergency. Al-Ameen et al. (2021) have argued that such a sporadic feature and its failure to become a critical component leads to technical issues having a detrimental impact on users' experiences and UCD principles in such apps. However, Kim et al. (2019) have come up with a solution, arguing that most users have favorable views about such apps as they believe this feature to be beneficial. What, however, is essential is to indicate the description of the devices that support this feature in some prominent place. Also, this feature should be given top priority due to its utility during emergencies, and developers must keep some issues such as interoperability, users' perception about it and overlading to resolve to make users have the best experience and ensure that the design adheres to the UCD principles.

One Touch Feature

Further observation of the statistics (Tabel 1) demonstrates that various apps have employed the One-Touch feature. This provides users with fast accessibility to critical functions of the apps. A total of 47% (8 out of 17 apps) show the use of this function. It also shows that integrating this feature has improved users' experience, providing them easy access to other functions. Based on UCD principles, this feature is critical, providing simple, straightforward and less overloaded accessibility with an explicit guarantee of getting clear and essential information. For example, Soni et al. (2023) prove the simplicity and clarity of the one-touch feature, adding that its usefulness is valid and has a beneficial impact on the users' experience. Yew et al. (2016) support him, adding that this function improves the useability of the app based on the user's experience, specifically for complicated apps, and users feel overloaded, putting more strains on their cognition. Although their features sync with UCD principles, the implementation issue still needs to be solved. For example, Sahebi et al. (2021) indicate various such issues, saying users find it challenging to understand due to the information's validity and subpar visual effects. Therefore, considering the environment where it is used and placing safety measures in place could reduce concerns related to useability. Striking a balance between minimalism and deviating from the path of using unintentional actions is essential to guarantee that the one-touch feature is practical in such evacuation apps used in emergencies. Therefore, the recommendation of using this feature in such apps helps improve the app experience, user experience and functionality of the elements. However, to achieve this objective, proactive measures are necessary. Guaranteeing this one-touch feature and its effectiveness in such a scenario requires a balance between minimizing usage features and unintentional action, as some users may unintentionally use this feature to cause alarm bells. Therefore, its integration must be given due consideration and priority during the design process, and this must be achieved through proactive measures.

Font Acuity

Another element identified to have affected accessibility due to readability is font acuity. The font of the text used in the apps must follow the UCD principles. Like all other elements, font acuity is also given priority when measuring the app on the yardstick of the UCD principal. Factors impacting font acuity range from vision to age and digital literacy to general literacy of the users. Therefore, font acuity regarding app usage is a necessary element. Several studies have focused on this aspect of the app designs to be integrated with guidelines about UCD principles. Du et al. (2023) believe that font size and type are critical, suggesting that body text should have 16 points while headings should have 18 to 24 points to make older users read it easily. Benson et al. (2005) on the other hand, focus on readability and clarity of the font usage and its type, adding that Arial or Helvetica, sans-serif or non-serif fonts are helpful for such interfaces to make readability sharp, focused and straightforward. Shneiderman et al. (2010) add line spacing to prevent congestion and increase readability, adding that line spacing, too, must adhere to the UCD principles. Beth Tondreau et al. (2019) a topographical specialist, also recommends point size ranging from 120 to 145 per cent, while Buchner et al. (2007) add the importance of the colour scheme to suggest high contrast colours as necessary to make text easily readable within the excellent background. This is because when contrast is low, it becomes difficult for readers to read quickly, and it also causes cognitive overloading due to eye strain. In short, font acuity principles must be followed in letter and spirit to enhance readability and user experience. Therefore, essential aspects of font acuity like font size, font type, line spacing and color contrast and color scheme, including background color must be given due consideration during the design process so that users' experience should take precedence over just designers' priorities.

3D model Design

Although 3D design benefits users by making their experience of using such apps superb and thoroughly engaging, the question of their

exclusion from the design process of such apps lingers without any unsatisfactory answer. Also, very few studies have turned attention to this aspect of apps, making it easy to evaluate the app of this principle in evacuation apps having a void. Academics suggest that the real problem lies in designing 3D models, which is complicated for such apps. For example, Ramadhani et al. (2023) state a dire need to integrate intuitive images according to the users' mental models. However, Mülazimoğlu et al. (2019) focus on understanding and clarity, such as shelter sides and routes through 3D modelling, clarifying that design must not be complicated. Oulasvirta et al. (2009) suggest the same things to increase users' overall experience using these apps, adding that 3D modelling should have user-friendly interaction. Lakovidis et al. (2020) stress the feature of accessibility, adding that this feature is critical in the 3D modelling of such apps as it also requires integration of the demography of the users. However, there are not only limits to technology but also to performance and user experience that cause issues in its integration into the interfaces of such apps (Mülazimoğlu, & Başaraner, 2019). Integrating 3D model design with a user-centric approach is essential to tackle these bottlenecks and roadblocks. Developers, therefore, must pay attention to its R&D issue to resolve and address the issues confronting its inclusion, adhering to the UCD principles. However, following these principles and working with tech experts on accessibility issues may yield positive results and find solutions to integrate these models into these apps. The gap may be closed through close coordination of all to make these apps effective and user-friendly.

Design for Impaired People

In every feature discussion, the concept of user-centered design (UCD) consistently emerges as a critical factor. This approach focuses on ease of use for the user, influencing decisions on which features to include or exclude. When considering diverse user types, especially those with disabilities, it is imperative to prioritize accessibility. Ensuring that our designs are inclusive and cater to the needs of all users aligns with the UCD principle of accessibility.

However, many apps fall short in this regard. For instance, only 47% (8 out of 17) of apps have features explicitly tailored for any disability, and visually impaired users often find themselves excluded from the design process. To encourage inclusivity and ensure that disabled users are considered in elemental designs, it is essential to remove roadblocks in the design process. Specific requirements of disabled people should be given due consideration. For example, Senjam et al. (2021) state that prioritizing accessibility features is crucial for creating a welcoming digital environment. Stefanov et al. (2022) support this view, arguing that UCD principles benefit users with impairments by allowing them to tailor their experience. Ntakolia et al. (2022) highlight that reducing cognitive overload in navigation processes is vital for impaired users, particularly in evacuation apps. Gilbert et al. (2019) stress an empathetic design approach, taking into account the specific difficulties faced by users with disabilities. Qureshi et al. (2019) focus on iteratively improving app design through user testing with a diverse population, including those with disabilities. Given the current absence of crucial accessibility features in many apps, incorporating these elements using UCD principles is imperative. This proactive approach ensures inclusivity and usability, enhancing the app experience for all users.

Multiple Tabs

According to the research, there is a common tendency whereby 59% (10 out of 17) of evacuation programs have chosen not to incorporate many tabs within their interface design. Developers' deliberate decision highlights issues with cognitive overload, obstructing access to essential data, and interfering with user navigation in multi-tab interfaces. Concerns of this kind are similar to UCD concepts, which support interface design that is clear and simple, especially for emergencies. Whether emergency evacuation apps that lack multi-tabs are consistent with UCD principles has generated discussion among scholars. While multi-tabs are intended to help organize content, Weinreich et al. (2008) point out that they may unintentionally add

complexity, hindering users' ability to access important information and make fast choices during evacuations. Similarly, Kodzhoshalieva (2020) investigate the matter and propose that adding several tabs may cause cognitive overload, impairing users' ability to digest important information efficiently. Furthermore, they contend that having too many tabs on the UI might needlessly complicate it in emergency scenarios when users should prioritize simplicity. This could make it difficult for users to find shelters, get timely notifications, and effectively use the program. Additional worries expressed by Kaur et al. (2020) highlight the possible accessibility issues that multi-tab interfaces may provide, especially for less tech-savvy or impaired users. They emphasize that intricate tab layouts would discourage certain users from using the program efficiently, eventually making it more difficult for them to react correctly in an emergency (Li, & Luximon, 2020). Based on these findings, scientists recommend simplifying the app structure following UCD principles to improve the efficiency of technology in emergency evacuation situations. Apps can provide a more user-friendly interface by stressing the importance of fewer tabs or utilizing dynamic components that adjust to the user's demands. This makes the program easier to use and speeds up decision-making in emergency scenarios (Ibrahim, et al., 2016).

Multi Language Feature

Another aspect often overlooked during the design process of such apps is the inclusion of multi-language features or support. This element is crucial as it significantly enhances the app's capability and aligns with a user-centric approach. Without multi-language support, users who are not familiar with the interface language may struggle to use the app effectively, limiting its accessibility and usability. Therefore, this feature must be prioritized with must-used elements. It optimizes the users' experience and leads to optimized usability and accessibility. Some other benefits include swift and easy communication for a diversity of users while adhering strictly to the principles of UCD. For the effectiveness of these apps in diverse regions with diverse people, multi-language ability

provides easy readability and easy response to disastrous events (Benavides, et al., 2021). In order to deliver inclusive and accessible information, UCD principles underline how important it is to take into account the language variety within a community so evacuation will be more effective and Vibal (Federici, 2022), but as we cover in the Font Acuity section, information alerts and notifications should adhere to the UCD principle. Specifically, section 1.8 outlines the appropriate font weight and style to be used, enabling users to quickly understand what to do next and how to safely evacuate in an emergency. Ross et al. (2016) state that user experience improves considerably along with engagement when multi-language capability is used in apps, which not only encourages the empowerment of the users but also makes it inclusive and exhaustive. Furthermore, this inclusion enhances accessibility and information proliferation among a wider audience and boosts the smoothness of the users' experience (Uekusa, & Matthewman, 2023). Therefore, prioritization of this feature also improves evacuation apps further to improve users' experience, leading to the effectiveness of these apps.

Color Schema

UCD strongly emphasizes following appropriate color schemes in evacuation apps due to their profound impact on user experience, accessibility, and communication effectiveness during emergencies. The following aspects, which were discussed, illustrate how adhering to UCD principles in color schema design improves evacuation apps. Several academics highlight important color schema concepts while creating evacuation apps with a UCD focus. In emergencies, UCD advises that color selections should put accessibility, understandability, and user comprehension first. High contrast color schemes are recommended by researchers like Linares-Vásquez, et al., (2015), Kaur & Dhindsa, (2022), and Lewandowska, et al., (2021) in their different findings, try to improve readability, particularly for users with visual impairments and how to reduce the energy consumption of mobile apps. Recommendations for Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG)

typically stress the need for adequate contrast ratios between background and text colors. Additionally, UCD promotes consistent color affordances, include green for safety and red for alerts to express meanings intuitively (Luna, et al., 017). Furthermore, scholars emphasize the significance of considering the cultural and symbolic connotations linked with hues to prevent possible misunderstandings (Ou, et al., 2012). However, Yigitbas et al. (2019) shed light on the fact that the foremost essential component is user feedback from usability testing, which enables designers to fine-tune color selections according to target audience preferences and perceptions. The inclusion of UCD concepts in color schema design should be given top priority by the designer in order to close this gap and improve evacuation apps. This will ensure user comprehension, accessibility, and clarity, and optimization will be achieved by utilizing user input.

First Aid instruction Feature

The last but not most minor feature that has won just 24% inclusion in these apps (4 out of 17) is also essential for evacuation apps. It indicates that most apps overlook this vital element, demonstrating a serious lack of understanding by the developers and designers. This feature is first aid information, which, though lower on the priority list, is of urgent necessity. Although comprehensive knowledge of first aid, specifically given to the users before such happenings, saves lives, its inclusion in such apps and their usage during critical moments enhances inclusivity per the UCD principles. Including and properly integrating this element ensures users' safety, awareness, and mental balance to prepare them to face the situation. Hence, the inclusion of this tab as per the UCD guidelines is critical when users' requirements are considered. Also, this integration must sync with the interface design requirements. Some researchers, including Loitsch, et al., (2017) and Gossen, et al., (2013) have shed light on its inclusion and significance in such apps. They are of the view that it increases readability, efficiency and clarity. Also, it synchs with Nielsen's usability benchmark about the user-friendly interface and clarity in communication (Jimenez,

Lozada, & Rosas, 2016). Moreover, when training this tab, users feel that they are already ready to face or confront such untoward happenings. Also, maximizing benefits and optimizing experience depend on following the UCD principle when designing the first aid tabs. This includes color, visual impact, concision of direction and multimodality in instructional design. Developers, therefore, when focusing on these aspects, increase the safety, readiness and confidence of the users through the provision of vital first-aid information.

Case Study of User-Centered Design in Emergency Preparedness Mobile Applications

In this section, we present two evacuation app case studies. Each of the two examples applies some of the features highlighted above. Our goal is to provide the readers with a detailed sense of how the features are utilized in apps and their

benefits and drawbacks. We evaluated these apps from two perspectives: user and developer. From the user perspective, we assessed the number of downloads, user reactions, reviews, and ratings. From the developer perspective, we used a set of UCD principles (Fig 1) and asked experienced developers to evaluate whether each feature adhered to UCD standards or they lacked in design.

SD Emergency App

This app aims to enhance disaster preparedness and response for users by ensuring that families are well-prepared when disaster strikes. The app allows users to create personalized plans and build comprehensive emergency supplies kits. During a disaster, the SD Emergency app provides critical updates, interactive emergency maps, shelter locations, and earthquake alerts. Additionally, the app offers a recovery section with valuable resources to aid during the aftermath of disasters. Some example pages are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Comprehensive Guide to SD Emergency App: Detailed Demonstration of Key Features and Step-by-Step Installation Instructions

User Perspective

The SD Emergency app integrates multiple features, include map visualization and push notifications. When assessing user perspectives based on reviews and ratings, positive feedback was received for several features, notably the

early warning system via push notifications and the clear path visualization on maps. Users appreciate the detailed and user-friendly nature of the maps, with comments as they said *The maps feature are clear and very useful.* Additionally, the Shelter Guide feature was praised for its well-organized design and ease of

navigation to nearby shelters, along with visualizing available space, whether there is any space left or not. However, some users noted that the map features could be improved by adding more detailed layers, as the density of emergencies shown in affected areas and real-time data on the current situation, like the direction of wildfires and the number of casualties. The Push Notifications feature was also highly regarded, with users describing it as a *Simple and Effective style of Notification*. Some users even highlighted its accessibility for impaired individuals, involve those who are deaf or hard of hearing, through sign language notifications as one said *thumbs up. They have thought of everyone, even those who are*

deaf/hard of hearing, via sign language. Despite these positive aspects, some users experienced delays and recommended real-time updates and customizable notification types, such as specifying the emergency category through push notification. Another analyzed feature was the First Aid Instructions, which received praise for their detail and ease of use. Suggestions included incorporating more visual aids and simplifying the language for quick reference. Overall, based on these reviews, it can be inferred that the app covers most aspects of user satisfaction and adheres to user-centered principles by continuously modifying and improving the app over time, as shown in Figure 4.

a. Pre Emergency Notification Feature

b. Push Notification

c. Map Based Visualization

d. First Aid Instruction

Figure 4. Highlighted Features of the SD Emergency Application: An In-Depth Analysis of Key Features Chosen for Their Alignment with UCD and Their Effectiveness in Enhancing Usability During Emergency Situations. You can receive the Pre emergency alerts in this tab (a); Receive all alerts messages in this tab (b); Map would be seen and help you to evacuate in this tab (c); You can see and learn about first Aid in this tab (d).

Developer Perspective

From a developer's standpoint, the SD Emergency app effectively adheres to UCD principles, yet there are targeted improvements that can enhance the user experience. Developers suggest optimizing the map visualization features, such as adding better evacuation path visuals or voice guidance

features for impaired people, ensuring that users can evacuate quickly. One developer noted *that lighting the map feature like unnecessary signage will significantly enhance user experience*. Some developers emphasized adding more detailed layers on the map, such as real-time data to show emergency density, to make the information more actionable. They

commented *that Incorporating real-time data layers into the map will provide users with critical information during fast-evolving situations*. They also noted that the notification feature should be more categorized, include visuals to illustrate the situation better, and provide more detailed information for enhanced clarity and user engagement. Developers appreciate the app's streamlined flow and minimalistic design, which enhance ease of use. They also value that each notification provides multiple options, enabling users to listen to or read the emergency information. This multimodal approach significantly improves the app's accessibility and usability, ensuring that it

caters to a diverse user base with varying preferences and needs.

Vic Emergency App

This app is designed to help users prepare for and respond to emergencies by providing timely alerts, evacuation maps, and safety tips. It offers real-time updates on fire incidents, allowing users to track emergency movements and receive notifications about nearby threats. The app also includes resources for creating an emergency plan and assembling a safety kit. Figure 5 illustrates the app's user interface and how to install and set the app watch zones.

Figure 5. Comprehensive Guide to VIC Emergency App: Detailed Demonstration of Key Features and Step-by-Step Installation Instructions

User Perspective

This app boasts an impressive 1 million downloads, suggesting significant user interest and trust. However, despite this popularity, it faces criticism for user engagement and satisfaction. For instance, despite the high download numbers, there are 4.49k reviews and an average rating of 3.5, indicating a gap in user feedback. The issues raised by users highlight significant concerns, such as excessive and irrelevant notifications, which can be frustrating for users. Also, notifications do not show the details of the incident; they only have simple icon pop-ups, especially when they need visual information about the incident. Additionally, users find that *[the] interface design of warning notifications is chaotic and geared*

towards a specific audience rather than catering to a wider user base. They also raised concerns about the map feature: it does not have Area filtration or evacuation path visuals like arrows and lines; they state *I received warnings from hundreds of kilometers away, and I can't filter it out on the map. It's like a cry-wolf situation*. Also, a few said *Map doesn't have an option that can give us any visuals, just give icon[s] about [the] emergency*. This fundamental lack of features in the map raises concerns about the app's dependency and reliability. Despite its drawbacks, some users appreciate the app's ease of use and extensive features, contains event filtration on the map or customizable warnings only alerts about events such as rain and fire. Users also praise the app

for showing the intensity of emergencies in real-time and providing pre-emergency notifications for better preparedness as one said, *This app makes me much safer in rural area[s]; being able to see what is going on in my surrounding and it is super easy to use.* However, a critical analysis reveals that the app falls short of User-Centered Design principles.

Its features often do not align with user needs, and the overall design is subpar. Additionally, the app lacks accessibility options for impaired users, raising concerns about its inclusivity. Nonetheless, the app remains popular due to its data authenticity and diverse features despite shortcomings in user experience design, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Highlighted Features of the VIC Emergency Application: An In-Depth Analysis of Key Features Chosen for Their Alignment with UCD and Their Effectiveness in Enhancing Usability During Emergency Situations. You can Filters the events in this tab (a); In this tab you can reactive the notification (b); In this Tab you can see the routes and visuals about different emergencies (c).

Developer Perspective

The analysis of the Vic Emergency app reveals commendable strengths in delivering real-time alerts and comprehensive emergency information. However, developers recognize the need for improvements based on their experience and user reviews. Few developers highlight the need for improvement in Color Schema. They said the *colors used in this app are unsuitable for an emergency app, as they lack the necessary impact.* They suggest revising the color scheme to include more vibrant, attention-grabbing

colors suitable for emergencies. Few developers emphasize redesigning the notification interface to include more detailed visual information about incidents, enhancing user engagement and satisfaction. As they mentioned, *Notifications serve as the initial point of contact with users, and if they lack engagement and responsiveness, the app's utility may diminish significantly.* Also, developers emphasized accessibility options for impaired users, stressing the importance of making the app inclusive and adhering to User-Centered

Design principles. Additionally, developers see the need for a more systematic approach to collecting and integrating user feedback to ensure continuous usability improvements like visuals in maps for evacuation. Despite its strengths in data authenticity and a diverse feature set, addressing these areas will significantly enhance the app's overall user experience and satisfaction.

Note: *These are developers individual thinking and are not final thoughts.*

Limitation

Firstly, we should note the limitations of our data collection. Although we filtered apps by their number of downloads, reviews, and ratings, we cannot accurately assess the actual quality of the app. In light of this, we emphasize the need for more comprehensive data and the potential impact of applying our taxonomy to more evacuation apps, making your contribution even more valuable.

Secondly, as mentioned earlier, the apps collected in this work mainly focus on evacuation scenarios. As such, we do not claim that our outcomes must be valid for other apps. By contrast, we acknowledge this limitation of our work. We treat our work as a starting point for formalizing apps according to user-centered design, and future work is required to further evaluate and modify our work.

We also acknowledge that there may be inevitable subjective bias when recognizing and categorizing a diverse set of features from an application. Our goal is to provide an approach to explain the characteristics and design of applications according to user-center design, for which purpose we believe our work is valid. Following our work, we envision that more additions could be added to finalize a systematic taxonomy.

Conclusion

In this paper, we highlight the importance of integrating UCD in the development of

emergency evacuation apps to enhance their usability, accessibility, and overall effectiveness during high-stress situations. We collected apps from different platforms such as the Google Play Store and Apple App Store using various keywords relevant to emergency evacuation. After filtering out the most relevant applications with high ratings and reviews, we identified key features essential for emergency applications and aligned them with UCD principles. We conducted research to determine which features are most commonly used in these applications and reviewed existing literature to understand the usability of these features, mentioning their flaws as noted in other research and the importance of aligning them with UCD principles. Subsequently, we conducted case studies on two of these applications, gathering user perspectives through comments and reviews, and developer perspectives through consultations with experienced developers to validate our analysis of these features. Our findings underscore the critical role of UCD in the development of evacuation apps, demonstrating that each feature should be designed with user needs in mind to ensure effective support during emergencies. The integration of UCD principles not only enhances the functionality and accessibility of these apps but also improves the overall user experience. After this research, we believe that our study provides valuable insights and motivates further research in this field. For future, we will incorporate direct data collection methods such as user questionnaires, interviews, and usability testing. These methods will gather valuable feedback from actual users, ensuring that the apps meet real-world needs and preferences. We also observed that cross-cultural, intracultural, and intercultural considerations through longitudinal studies and global research to enhance the global usefulness and usability of these apps. This approach will enable continuous improvement and adaptation of evacuation apps, empowering users during critical emergency situations.

Reference

- Al Bochi, A., Roberts, B. W., Sajid, W., Ghulam, Z., Weiler, M., Sharma, Y., et al. (2023). Evacuation solutions for individuals with functional limitations in the indoor built environment: A scoping review. *Buildings*, 13(11), 2779. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13112779>
- Al-Akkad, A., Zimmermann, A., Birlinghoven, S., & Augustin, S. (2011, May). User study: Involving civilians by smart phones during emergency situations. In *ISCRAM*.
- Al-Ameen, M. N., Tamanna, T., Nandy, S., & Kocabas, H. (2021, July). Understanding user behavior, information exposure, and privacy risks in managing old devices. In *International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction* (pp. 281–296). Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78233-9_23
- Alexander, D. E. (2015). *Disaster and emergency planning for preparedness, response, and recovery*. Oxford University Press.
- Benavides, A. D., Nukpezah, J., Keyes, L. M., & Soujaa, I. (2021). Adoption of multilingual state emergency management websites: Responsiveness to the risk communication needs of a multilingual society. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 44(5), 409–419. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01900692.2020.1837987>
- Benson, J., Olewiler, K., & Broden, N. (2005, November). Typography for mobile phone devices: The design of the Qualcomm sans font family. In *Proceedings of the 2005 Conference on Designing for User Experience* (pp. 58–es).
- Bernardini, G., Santarelli, S., Quagliarini, E., & D’Orazio, M. (2017). Dynamic guidance tool for a safer earthquake pedestrian evacuation in urban systems. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 65, 150–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2017.06.003>
- Biswas, P., Robinson, P., & Langdon, P. (2012). Designing inclusive interfaces through user modeling and simulation. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 28(1), 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2011.622110>
- Boy, G. A. (2017). Human-centered design of complex systems: An experience-based approach. *Design Science*, 3, e8. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dsj.2017.9>
- Buchner, A., & Baumgartner, N. (2007). Text-background polarity affects performance irrespective of ambient illumination and colour contrast. *Ergonomics*, 50(7), 1036–1063. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140130701311353>
- Cao, Y., Boruff, B. J., & McNeill, I. M. (2016). Is a picture worth a thousand words? Evaluating the effectiveness of maps for delivering wildfire warning information. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 19, 179–196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2016.08.012>
- Carroll, J. M., & Rosson, M. B. (2014). *Usability engineering*.
- Catarci, T., Marrella, A., Santucci, G., Sharf, M., Vitaletti, A., Di Lucchio, L., et al. (2020). From consensus to innovation: Evolving towards crowd-based user-centered design. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 36(15), 1460–1475. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2020.1759906>
- Chen, A., Zhu, H., Ni, X., & Su, G. (2020). Pre-warning information dissemination models of different media under emergencies. *Chinese Physics B*, 29(9), 094302. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1674-1056/ab95df>
- Chua, W. Y., & Chang, K. T. (2016, January). An investigation of usability of push notifications on mobile devices for novice and expert users. In *2016 49th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS)* (pp. 5683–5690). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2016.705>
- Cotfas, L. A., Delcea, C., Mancini, S., Ponsiglione, C., & Vitiello, L. (2023). An agent-based model for cruise ship evacuation considering the presence of smart technologies on board. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 214, 119124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.119124>

- Cybulski, P. (2021). Effectiveness of memorizing an animated route—comparing satellite and road map differences in the eye-tracking study. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 10(3), 159. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi10030159>
- Dirgahayu, T., & Setiaji, H. (2021). A context-aware mobile application for disaster preparedness of people in disaster-prone areas. *ICIC Express Letters. Part B, Applications: An International Journal of Research and Surveys*, 12(9), 773–780.
- Dong, W., Yu, C., & Zhibin, M. (2018, November). Study of sound direction evacuation. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1107, No. 7, p. 072002). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1107/7/072002>
- Du, H., Liu, W., Wang, P., Sun, X., & Zhang, W. (2023, July). The influence of background color and font size of mobile payment app interface on elderly user experience. In *International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction* (pp. 392–401). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-13251-6_33
- Du, P., Li, D., Liu, T., Zhang, L., Yang, X., & Li, Y. (2021). Crisis map design considering map cognition. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 10(10), 692. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi10100692>
- Federici, F. M. (2022). Translating hazards: Multilingual concerns in risk and emergency communication. *The Translator*, 28(4), 375–398. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2022.2100612>
- Ferris, T., Moreno-Centeno, E., Yates, J., Sung, K., El-Sherif, M., & Matarrita-Cascante, D. (2016). Studying the usage of social media and mobile technology during extreme events and their implications for evacuation decisions: A case study of Hurricane Sandy. *International Journal of Mass Emergencies & Disasters*, 34(2), 204–230.
- Figueiredo, D. A. (2019). *Applying the User-Centered Design approach for Prototyping the Interfaces of an Intelligent Emergency Management System* [Doctoral dissertation].
- Freeman, J., Park, S., & Middleton, C. (2020). Technological literacy and interrupted internet access. *Information, Communication & Society*, 23(13), 1947–1964. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2019.1670224>
- Gai, W. M., Du, Y., & Deng, Y. F. (2018). Evacuation risk assessment of regional evacuation for major accidents and its application in emergency planning: A case study. *Safety Science*, 106, 203–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2018.03.015>
- Gilbert, R. M. (2019). *Inclusive design for a digital world: Designing with accessibility in mind*. Apress. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4842-4794-7>
- Gossen, T., Nitsche, M., Vos, J., & Nürnberger, A. (2013, October). Adaptation of a search user interface towards user needs: A prototype study with children & adults. In *Proceedings of the Symposium on Human-Computer Interaction and Information Retrieval* (pp. 1–10). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2517820.2517832>
- Haghani, M., Sarvi, M., & Shahhoseini, Z. (2020). Evacuation behaviour of crowds under high and low levels of urgency: Experiments of reaction time, exit choice and exit-choice adaptation. *Safety Science*, 126, 104679. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.104679>
- Hass, C. (2019). A practical guide to usability testing. In *Consumer Informatics and Digital Health: Solutions for Health and Health Care* (pp. 107–124). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-22958-6_6
- Iakovidis, D. K., Diamantis, D., Dimas, G., Ntakolia, C., & Spyrou, E. (2020). Digital enhancement of cultural experience and accessibility for the visually impaired. In *Technological Trends in Improved Mobility of the Visually Impaired* (pp. 237–271). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-37897-0_10
- Ibrahim, A. M., Venkat, I., Subramanian, K., Khader, A. T., & Wilde, P. D. (2016). Intelligent evacuation management systems: A review.

ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology (TIST), 7(3), 1-27.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/2895995>

Jimenez, C., Lozada, P., & Rosas, P. (2016, September). Usability heuristics: A systematic review. In *2016 IEEE 11th Colombian Computing Conference (CCC)* (pp. 1-8). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ColumbianCC.2016.7791181>

Kamilaris, A., Filippi, J. B., Padubidri, C., Koole, R., & Karatsiolis, S. (2023). Examining the potential of mobile applications to assist people to escape wildfires in real-time. *Fire Safety Journal*, 136, 103747.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.firesaf.2023.103747>

Kanangkaew, S., Jokkaw, N., & Tongthong, T. (2023). A real-time fire evacuation system based on the integration of building information modeling and augmented reality. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 67, 105883.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2023.105883>

Kaur, S., & Dhindsa, K. S. (2020). Design and development of android-based mobile application for specially abled people. *Wireless Personal Communications*, 111, 2353-2367.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11277-019-06774-5>

Kaur, S., & Dhindsa, K. S. (2022). IFSA: An integrated framework for developing IoT linked mobile applications for specially abled people. *Wireless Networks*, 28(4), 1375-1388.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11276-022-02793-w>

Kim, G., Martel, A., Eisenman, D., Prelip, M., Arevian, A., Johnson, K. L., & Glik, D. (2019). Wireless emergency alert messages: Influences on protective action behaviour. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 27(4), 374-386. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-5973.12212>

Kitsuya, M., Tsukahara, R., & Sasaki, J. (2021). Development of Real-Time Evacuation Support System (RESS) to reduce human damage in natural disasters. In *Information Technology in Disaster Risk Reduction: 5th IFIP WG 5.15 International Conference, ITDRR 2020, Sofia, Bulgaria, December 3-4, 2020, Revised Selected Papers* (pp. 14-25). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80564-0_2

Kodzhoshalieva, A. (2020). Reducing cognitive load for a data-intensive web application user. *Procedia Computer Science*, 176, 417-426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.09.058>

Krauß, V., Boden, A., Oppermann, L., & Reiners, R. (2021, May). Current practices, challenges, and design implications for collaborative AR/VR application development. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1-15). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445122>

Kuo, T. W., Lin, C. Y., Chuang, Y. J., & Hsiao, G. L. K. (2022). Using smartphones for indoor fire evacuation. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(10), 6061. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19106061>

Lewandowska, A., Olejnik-Krugly, A., Jankowski, J., & Dziśko, M. (2021). Subjective and objective user behavior disparity: Towards balanced visual design and color adjustment. *Sensors*, 21(24), 8502.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/s21248502>

Li, M., Xu, J., Liu, X., Sun, C., & Duan, Z. (2018). Use of shared-mobility services to accomplish emergency evacuation in urban areas via reduction in intermediate trips: Case study in Xi'an, China. *Sustainability*, 10(12), 4862. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10124862>

Li, Q., & Luximon, Y. (2020). Older adults' use of mobile device: Usability challenges while navigating various interfaces. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 39(8), 837-861.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2020.1764985>

Lin, J., Zhu, R., Li, N., & Becerik-Gerber, B. (2020). How occupants respond to building emergencies: A systematic review of behavioral characteristics and behavioral theories. *Safety Science*, 122, 104540.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2019.104540>

Linares-Vásquez, M., Bavota, G., Cárdenas, C. E. B., Oliveto, R., Di Penta, M., & Poshyvanyk, D. (2015, August). Optimizing energy consumption of GUIs in Android apps: A multi-objective approach. In *Proceedings of the 2015 10th Joint Meeting on Foundations of Software Engineering*

(pp. 143-154). ACM.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/2786805.2786812>

Liu, M., Zhang, F., Ma, Y., Pota, H. R., & Shen, W. (2016). Evacuation path optimization based on quantum ant colony algorithm. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 30(3), 259–267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2016.03.002>

Loitsch, C., Weber, G., Kaklanis, N., Votis, K., & Tzovaras, D. (2017). A knowledge-based approach to user interface adaptation from preferences and for special needs. *User Modeling and User-Adapted Interaction*, 27, 445-491. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11257-017-9209-3>

Luna, D. R., Ledesma, D. A. R., Otero, C. M., Risk, M. R., & de Quirós, F. G. B. (2017). User-centered design improves the usability of drug-drug interaction alerts: Experimental comparison of interfaces. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 66, 204-213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2017.01.006>

Marrella, A., Mecella, M., & Russo, A. (2011). Collaboration on-the-field: Suggestions and beyond. In *8th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management (ISCRAM 2011)*.

Méndez-Gurrola, I. I., Barraza-Castillo, R. I., Ramírez Reyes, A., & Barranco-Gutiérrez, A. I. (2023, July). An approach to mobile app design and development combining design thinking, user experience, and iterative-incremental development. In *Science and Information Conference* (pp. 623–638). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-35169-2_46

Mülazimoğlu, E., & Başaraner, M. (2019). User-centered design and evaluation of multimodal tourist maps. *International Journal of Engineering and Geosciences*, 4(3), 115–128.

Nefros, K. C., Kitsara, G. S., & Photis, Y. N. (2018). Using geographic information systems (GIS) to develop prioritization maps in urban search and rescue operations after a natural disaster: Case study: The municipality of Agia Paraskevi, Athens, Greece. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 51(30), 360–365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2018.11.124>

Nóbrega, R., Cabral, D., Jacucci, G., & Coelho, A. (2015, March). NARI: Natural augmented reality interface-interaction challenges for AR applications. In *International Conference on Computer Graphics Theory and Applications* (Vol. 2, pp. 504–510). SCITEPRESS. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0005328905040510>

Ntakolia, C., Dimas, G., & Iakovidis, D. K. (2022). User-centered system design for assisted navigation of visually impaired individuals in outdoor cultural environments. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-022-00773-w>

Omaier, H. T., Alharbi, A. Z., Alotaibi, M. F., & Ibrahim, D. M. (2019). Comparative study between emergency response mobile applications. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS)*, 17(2), 87–91.

Ortakci, Y., Atila, U., Demiral, E., Ozacar, K., & Karas, I. R. (2017). Comparison of a smart mobile application-supported evacuation system and traditional evacuation systems. In *1st IAG Workshop on BIM and GIS Integration*.

Ou, L. C., Ronnier Luo, M., Sun, P. L., Hu, N. C., Chen, H. S., Guan, S. S., ... & Richter, K. (2012). A cross-cultural comparison of colour emotion for two-colour combinations. *Color Research & Application*, 37(1), 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.1002/col.20709>

Oulasvirta, A., Estlander, S., & Nurminen, A. (2009). Embodied interaction with a 3D versus 2D mobile map. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, 13, 303–320. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00779-008-0204-6>

Paul, J. D., Bee, E., & Budimir, M. (2021). Mobile phone technologies for disaster risk reduction. *Climate Risk Management*, 32, 100296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2021.100296>

Qureshi, H. H., & Wong, D. H. T. (2019). A systematic literature review on user-centered design (UCD) interface of mobile application for visually impaired people. In *HCI International 2019—Late Breaking Posters: 21st HCI International Conference, HCII 2019, Orlando, FL, USA, July 26–31, 2019, Proceedings 21* (pp. 168-175). Springer International Publishing.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-23531-2_19

Radianti, J., Granmo, O. C., Bouhmala, N., Sarshar, P., Yazidi, A., & Gonzalez, J. (2013, January). Crowd models for emergency evacuation: A review targeting human-centered sensing. In *2013 46th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences* (pp. 156–165). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2013.456>

Ramadhani, S. R., & Limin, F. S. (2023). Improving learning motivation by applying user-centered design and augmented reality on 3D interactive application. *JITK (Jurnal Ilmu Pengetahuan dan Teknologi Komputer)*, *9*(1), 8–16.

Romano, M., Onorati, T., Aedo, I., & Diaz, P. (2016). Designing mobile applications for emergency response: Citizens acting as human sensors. *Sensors*, *16*(3), 406. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s16030406>

Ronchi, E., Corbetta, A., Galea, E. R., Kinateder, M., Kuligowski, E., McGrath, D., & Toschi, F. (2019). New approaches to evacuation modelling for fire safety engineering applications. *Fire Safety Journal*, *106*, 197–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.firesaf.2019.04.004>

Ross, J., & Gao, J. (2016). Overcoming the language barrier in mobile user interface design: A case study on a mobile health app. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1605.04693*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1605.04693>

Ruggiero, L. (2018). A review of augmented reality applications for building evacuation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.04186*.

Ryan, B., Johnston, K. A., Taylor, M., & McAndrew, R. (2020). Community engagement for disaster preparedness: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, *49*, 101655. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101655>

Sahebi, A., Jahangiri, K., Alibabaei, A., & Khorasani-Zavareh, D. (2021). Factors influencing hospital emergency evacuation during fire: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Preventive Medicine*, *12*, 43. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijpvm.IJPVM_160_20

Sarshar, P., Nunavath, V., & Radianti, J. (2015). On the usability of smartphone apps in emergencies: An HCI analysis of GDACSmobile and SmartRescue apps. In *Human-Computer Interaction: Interaction Technologies: 17th International Conference, HCI International 2015, Los Angeles, CA, USA, August 2–7, 2015, Proceedings, Part II* (pp. 765–774). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-20916-6_71

Sarshar, P., Radianti, J., & Gonzalez, J. J. (2015). On the impacts of utilizing smartphones on organizing rescue teams and evacuation procedures. In *ISCRAM 2015 Conference Proceedings*.

Senjam, S. S., Manna, S., & Bascaran, C. (2021). Smartphones-based assistive technology: Accessibility features and apps for people with visual impairment, and its usage, challenges, and usability testing. *Clinical Optometry*, 311–322.

Sharma, S., Stigall, J., & Bodempudi, S. T. (2020, March). Situational awareness-based augmented reality instructional (ARI) module for building evacuation. In *2020 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)* (pp. 70–78). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/VRW50115.2020.00021>

Shneiderman, B., & Plaisant, C. (2010). *Designing the user interface: Strategies for effective human-computer interaction* (5th ed.). Pearson Education India.

Sikder, M. F., Halder, S., Hasan, T., Uddin, M. J., & Baowaly, M. K. (2017, September). Smart disaster notification system. In *2017 4th International Conference on Advances in Electrical Engineering (ICAEE)* (pp. 658–663). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAEE.2017.8255432>

Soni, A., Dalal, A., Chaurasia, K., & Singh, M. P. (2023, August). Emergency response app for enhancing location-based services using socket.io and WebRTC. In *2023 International Conference on Electrical, Electronics, Communication and Computers (ELEXCOM)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ELEXCOM56185.2023.10107591>

- Stefanov, T., Varbanova, S., & Stefanova, M. (2022). Mobile devices supporting people with special needs. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 13(11). <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2022.0131184>
- Stigall, J., & Sharma, S. (2019, September). Evaluation of mobile augmented reality application for building evacuation. In *Proceedings of 28th International Conference* (Vol. 64, pp. 109–118).
- Suzianti, A., Wulandari, A. D., Yusuf, A. H., Belahakki, A., & Monika, F. (2020, January). Design thinking approach for mobile application design of disaster mitigation management. In *Proceedings of the 2020 2nd Asia Pacific Information Technology Conference* (pp. 29–33). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3379310.3379338>
- Tan, M. L., Prasanna, R., Stock, K., Doyle, E. E., Leonard, G., & Johnston, D. (2020). Understanding end-users' perspectives: Towards developing usability guidelines for disaster apps. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 7, 100118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pdisas.2020.100118>
- Tanaka, T., Matsuda, Y., Fujimoto, M., Suwa, H., & Yasumoto, K. (2021). Evacuation shelter decision method considering non-cooperative evacuee behavior to support the disaster weak. *Sustainability*, 13(9), 5106. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13095106>
- Tondreau, B. (2019). *Layout essentials revised and updated: 100 design principles for using grids*. Rockport Publishers.
- Traya, R. V., Verona, R. M. P., Malatbalat, L. A. A., Nuevas, L. K., Obediencia, D. C., Velarde, M. W. C., & Daylo, R. M. (2022, September). Android mobile application: Tsunami alert system with an escape route for evacuation in municipal disaster risk reduction and management office. In *2022 Fifth International Conference on Vocational Education and Electrical Engineering (ICVEE)* (pp. 30-35). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICVEE55647.2022.9881027>
- Uekusa, S., & Matthewman, S. (2023). Preparing multilingual disaster communication for the crises of tomorrow: A conceptual discussion. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 87, 103589. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2023.103589>
- Weinreich, H., Obendorf, H., Herder, E., & Mayer, M. (2008). Not quite the average: An empirical study of Web use. *ACM Transactions on the Web (TWEB)*, 2(1), 1-31. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1341430.1341432>
- Wohlebe, A., Adler, M. R., & Podruzsik, S. (2021). Influence of design elements of mobile push notifications on mobile app user interactions. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 15(15), 35–46. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v15i15.24787>
- Wu, D., Moody, G. D., Zhang, J., & Lowry, P. B. (2020). Effects of the design of mobile security notifications and mobile app usability on users' security perceptions and continued use intention. *Information & Management*, 57(5), 103235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2019.103235>
- Xia, X., Li, N., & González, V. A. (2021). Exploring the influence of emergency broadcasts on human evacuation behavior during building emergencies using virtual reality technology. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 35(2), 04020065. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CP.1943-5487.0000962](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CP.1943-5487.0000962)
- Yew, L. K., Baharudin, A. S., & Karkonasasi, K. (2016). Touch-aid: The impact of user factors on users' intention to adopt location-based mobile application for emergency services. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 11(19), 9990–9993.
- Yigitbas, E., Hottung, A., Rojas, S. M., Anjorin, A., Sauer, S., & Engels, G. (2019). Context-and data-driven satisfaction analysis of user interface adaptations based on instant user feedback. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 3(EICS), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3324914>
- Zhang, M., Xu, R., Siu, M. F. F., & Luo, X. (2023). Human decision change in crowd evacuation: A virtual reality-based study. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 68, 106041. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2023.106041>

Zhang, N., Ni, X. Y., Huang, H., Zhao, J. L., Duarte, M., & Zhang, J. (2016). The impact of interpersonal pre-warning information

dissemination on regional emergency evacuation. *Natural Hazards*, 80, 2081–2103. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-015-2054-y>

Table 1. Comprehensive Evaluation Features for Emergency Evacuation Mobile Applications

Link	App Name	One touch Feature	Pre-Emergency Notification Feature	Map Based Visualization	AR based direction visualization Feature	Shelter guide Feature	First Aid instruction feature	Push Notification	Voice/Sound guidance feature	3D model Design	Design for impaired People	Multi Language feature	Multiple tabs	Font acuity	Color Schema
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=kr.go.nema.dicasteralert_eng	Emergency Ready App	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	Better	Better
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=ca.ab.gov.aas	Albert Emergency Alert	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	Better	Much Better
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.ab.wildfire	AB Wildfire Status	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	Excellent	good
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.safetrolapp.safetrol	Noonlight: Feel Protected 24/7	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	Excellent	Better
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.navigateemergencymanagementuite	Emergency Management Suite	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	Better	Worse
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.csl411.ier	Integrated Emergency Response	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	Better	Good
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.naturallybeing.fireready	Vic Emergency	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	Better	worse
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.mysofamily	My SOS Family Emergency Alerts	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	Better	good
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=org.CountyofSanDiego.SDEmergency	SD Emergency	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	Excellent	worse
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.guard_eye.evac	EVAC	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	Better	good
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=kz.khkh.schoolvacuation	Evacuation	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	Better	Better
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=net.eoj.JaxReady	Jax Ready	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	Excellent	worse
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=jp.co.rcsc.safetyTips.android	Safety Tips	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	Better	Good
https://apps.apple.com/cn/app/msi-emergency-navigation/id683003070?l=en-GB	MSI Emergency Navigation	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	Excellent	Better
https://apps.apple.com/cn/app/storm-evacuation/id196923511?l=en-GB	Storm Evacuation	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	Better	Good
https://apps.apple.com/cn/app/closecircle/id1318175676?l=en-GB	Close Circle	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	Excellent	worse
https://apps.apple.com/cn/app/shibuya-arrow-project/id1451635167?l=en-GB	Shibuya Arrow Project	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	Excellent	Bad